

TREATMENT OF DESTRUCTIVE-INFLAMMATION PROCESS IN ORAL CAVITY TISSUES IN WOMEN WITH OSTEOPOROSIS DURING THE PERIOD OF MENOPAUSE

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Research relevance: Common osteoporosis in perimenopausal and menopausal women can be compared to the epidemic of the 21st century. Despite the lack of information about the pathogenesis of the disease, the available information already allows the development of treatment principles and preventive measures in this contingent of women. This article provides information on the pathogenesis, clinical presentation, principles of treatment, and preventive features of osteoporosis in adults.

The purpose of the study: to determine the common risk factors in the origin of osteoporosis in women and to study their impact on the organs of the oral cavity, treatment of stomatological diseases

Research material and methods: During the research period, 150 menopausal and postmenopausal women aged 45-55 years old, aged 45-55, with osteoporosis based on osteoporosis, were conducted in 2020-2022 on the basis of the Department of Therapeutic Dentistry of the Bukhara State Medical Institute. women without osteoporosis were examined. Women between the ages of 45 and 55 are considered to be at high risk for osteoporosis during menopause. Age levels of women based on osteoporosis during menopause are compiled according to the WHO classification

Results and analysis: Patients with moderate and severe destructive-inflammation in oral cavity tissues against the background of osteoporosis during menopause were examined in the dynamics of treatment. Professional hygiene measures and standard treatment measures were carried out in the oral cavity.

In order to determine the most effective method of correcting mineral metabolism with drugs before periodontological treatment of patients with destructive-inflammation of oral cavity tissues against the background of osteoporosis during menopause, 40 women with osteoporosis during menopause were included. Female patients in this group were divided into 2 groups.

The main group consisted of 24 patients, during the period of preparation for periodontal treatment, 2 tablets of Teraflex-Advance, Dentazol gel for the treatment and prevention of periodontal tissue, and Coconut oil for 10 days were prescribed. The comparison group consisted of 20 patients who received "Calcium D3 Nikomed" and "metrogyl denta" for 12 months. The control group consisted of 32 patients with periodontitis of normal childbearing age.

The effectiveness of the treatment was determined according to the following criteria: index evaluation of periodontal condition, orthopantomography, Periotestometric data, markers of bone tissue remodeling in the oral cavity, microbiological. The effectiveness of treatment was studied 2 months after the start of therapy, 6 months and 12 months after the end of therapy (survey, clinical-laboratory studies).

Regression analysis of subjective and objective symptoms of the disease showed that 2 months after the onset of the disease, remission of moderate periodontitis against the background of osteoporosis was noted in all patients, and remission of severe periodontitis was observed in 91.7% of patients in group A ($r > 0.05$)

After the treatment, the values of indices describing inflammatory-destructive processes in the periodontium decreased statistically significantly, hygiene in the oral cavity improved, but the indicators of gum regeneration remained unchanged.

In orthopantomography, stabilization of the pathological process was noted when clinical remission of periodontal disease was achieved in all patients, as confirmed by the Fuchs index and cortical index indicators, which did not change

statistically significantly compared to the data before the start of treatment in the compared groups

Re-examination was carried out 6 months after the beginning of periodontological treatment and osteoporosis correction processes. After 6 months, remission of moderate periodontitis was maintained in 83.3% of female patients in the comparison group and 88.9% of female patients in the main group, severe periodontitis remission was achieved in 75% of patients in the comparison group and 83.3% of patients in the main group. It is necessary to mention that all female patients were motivated to receive treatment, which allowed to maintain the achieved level of hygiene in the oral cavity.

Osteosynthesis marker - osteocalcin increased and bone tissue resorption marker - C-terminal telopeptide collagen type 1 decreased in the oral fluid of all patients with general periodontitis during menopause 6 months after the start of treatment. The positive dynamics of the levels of osteocalcin and C-terminal telopeptide collagen type 1 was more reliable in the group of patients receiving bisphosphonates.

Monitoring of reliable markers provides valuable information about antiresorptive treatment long before the change and allows assessment of response to treatment 2 months after the start of complex therapy. It can be concluded that osteocalcin and C-terminal telopeptide collagen 1 can be used as markers for early evaluation of the effectiveness of general periodontitis treatment in postmenopausal women with osteoporosis.

Conclusion: Thus, osteoporosis is a disease characterized by a decrease in bone mineral density and a violation of the microarchitecture of bone tissue. It is more common in women during perimenopause. Among the risk factors that cause this disease, factors such as lack of Ca in the blood, vitamin D deficiency, and taking glucocorticoids for more than 3 months are the leading factors. is occupying General osteoporosis in women causes dental diseases and requires the organization of dental care in women in this contingent.

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